

Challenges for Cultural Tourism & Sustainability of the World Heritage Site of Angkor, Cambodia

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Abstract

Cambodia, a culturally significant country in South-East Asia draws the attention of several tourists for its ancient culture and heritage. It is well-known for the ancient civilization of Khmer centered in Angkor. As a result, Angkor has become a one-of-a-kind symbol of this ancient civilisation and the Cambodian country as a whole. In the year 1992 Angkor Archaeological Park, in Siem Reap, Cambodia, became a World Heritage Site. It was included on the List of World Heritage in Danger. The APSARA National Authority, monitored by the ICC-Angkor, took great initiatives in conserving the sites. These efforts finally lead to the removal of the property from the World Heritage List in danger in 2004. Since then, Angkor and Siem reap have become a prime focus for cultural tourism. The location attracts a large number of tourists from all around the world. This has resulted in more visitor traffic than the region's cultural and physical infrastructure can sustain. Thus, Angkor is seeing some economic and social progress, as well as a slew of serious challenges that have cropped up as a consequence of the development process. Cultural tourism has on one hand given a thrust for financial, social and economic development while on the other has brought about a threat for sustainability and heritage management in the region. This paper aims to highlight the boons of cultural tourism and the major threats it poses for sustainable development and heritage management principles of the ancient sites of Angkor. The study encompasses the positive effects and possible threats of cultural tourism in Angkor.

Key Words: Cultural tourism, World heritage, Angkor

Introduction

Cultural tourism is regarded as a branch of Tourism. This branch of tourism deals with leisure travel usually motivated by one or more aspects of the culture of a particular region or country. Various aspects of human culture and built heritages form the basis of cultural tourism. A number of tourists across the world are attracted due to the culture & heritage of a country. However, cultural tourism can be regarded as a multidimensional segment of the 'tourism sector,' with a diversified and dynamic supply (Csapó, 2012).

There are different definitions of Cultural tourism. One of the most diverse and specific definitions are given by ICOMOS (International Scientific Committee on Cultural Tourism): “Cultural tourism can be defined as that activity which enables people to experience the

different ways of life of other people, thereby gaining at first hand, an understanding of their customs, traditions, the physical environment, the intellectual ideas and those places of architectural, historic, archaeological or other cultural significance which remain from earlier times. Cultural tourism differs from recreational tourism in that it seeks to gain an understanding or appreciation of the nature of the place being visited” (ICOMOS, 1997)

Another definition given by Stebbins (1996) states that “Cultural tourism is a genre of special interest tourism based on the search for and participation in new and deep cultural experiences, whether aesthetic, or intellectual”.

Cultural tourism portrays the different aspects of human culture, heritage, natural resources of a certain area or nation. Tourists are more interested in visiting different heritage and archaeological sites & monuments. It has been observed that the heritage travellers stay longer at their destinations and spend more money there than other types of travellers.

Cultural tourists can be classified into five categories (Fig.1) as suggested by Mckercher, on the basis of centrality and intensity of experience (Mckercher, 2002).

Figure 1: Classification of cultural tourists

The purposeful cultural tourists – represent the group of individuals with high motivation and enjoy a very rich and intricate cultural experience since cultural tourism is the major driving factor for visiting a destination.

The sightseeing cultural tourists – Although cultural tourism is a key motivation for travelling to a certain location, the experience is less in-depth and detailed for this type of tourists.

The serendipitous cultural tourists – Tourists who do not visit for cultural purposes but appear to be having a rich cultural tourism experience as a result of their participation are regarded as serendipitous cultural tourists.

The casual cultural tourists – For such tourists, cultural tourism is not a major reason to travel, so the experience that results is superficial.

The incidental cultural tourists –This category of tourists does not seem to be motivated by cultural purposes, although he or she does engage in certain events and has a limited amount of experience.

The varied definitions of cultural tourism can be thus classified into four groups such as: tourism derived, motivational, experiential and operational (McKercher & Du Cros, 2002).

However, the growing interest leading to a huge influx of visitors requires a well-developed infrastructure which can put a major strain on the very resources that attract the visitors in the first place. The natural, cultural resources have a high chance of damage as the number of visitors and local tourism industry increases. It is imperative to protect those cultural heritage resources while attracting the tourists.

Cultural Tourism & Sustainability

A growing concern of the present generation of human beings is the preservation and management of the resources and the heritages. In the attempt to solve this problem, the concept of Sustainable development has emerged in recent times. Sustainable development is a pattern of resource use that aims to meet human needs while preserving the environment so that these needs can be met not only in the present, but also for future generations. The term was first used by the Brundtland Commission., 1987. According to this concept a nation or a society should be able to satisfy its need--- social, economic and others without jeopardizing the interest of the future generations. Sustainability requires that human activity only uses nature's resources at a rate at which they can be replenished naturally. This concept of Sustainability backed by biological, economic and more rarely, cultural and social arguments, made its appearance in the mid-80s, with a marked emphasis on environmental protection. It involves both the factors --safeguarding and development. With the changing scenario sustainability now has a much wider aspect and is holistic in nature. Now a days sustainability is being associated to other important elements apart from environment such as the social, cultural and economic dimensions.

Thus, the idea considers long term social solidarity, enhancement of cultural diversity, protection of the environment and economic growth as essential components of the sustainable framework as a whole. Since the Johannesburg summit the cultural dimension has become an integral part of sustainability thereby changing the notion of sustainable development into a more holistic concept.

One of the principal objectives of cultural heritage tourism is collaboration with local organizations and the public to develop sustainable economies. Tourism creates jobs, new business opportunities, and strengthens local economies. Apart from sustainable economies cultural tourism leads to the sustainability of natural & cultural resources. It protects natural and cultural resources, which improve the quality of life for residents and travellers who participate in the services and attractions. Heritage tourism also promotes community pride by allowing people to work together to enhance economic and cultural development through distinct community engagements. Studies show that travellers are keener to visit places with a strong community identity. Thus, cultural tourism not only provides economic development but also social, environmental & cultural sustainability of a nation.

Angkor Wat- The World Heritage Site

Cambodia, a culturally significant country in South-East Asia draws the attention of several tourists for its ancient culture and heritage. It is well-known for the ancient civilization of Khmer centred in Angkor (Fig.2&3). Angkor has thus been a unique icon of this ancient civilization and the Cambodian nation as a whole. The Angkor Archaeological Park, in Siem Reap, Cambodia, was designated as a World Heritage Site in 1992. It was added to the List of Endangered World Heritage Sites. The APSARA National Authority, which was overseen by the ICC-Angkor, took significant steps to preserve the sites. These efforts eventually resulted in the site being removed off the endangered World Heritage List in 2004. Since then, Angkor and Siem Reap have become popular tourist destinations.

Angkor Wat, a UNESCO World Heritage Site, is going through one of its most critical and tumultuous times in its 1200-year existence. Over 20 nations have given millions of dollars to assist protect and repair its temples since the early 1990s. In just over a decade, Angkor has experienced a 10,000 percent increase in foreign visitor visits, making it one of Southeast Asia's most popular attractions. The difficulties posed by the intense confluence of these two contradictory and insecure agendas—heritage protection and tourism development—are amplified by Cambodia's desire to recover from conflict and upheaval. At this juncture, it is important to investigate the patterns of tourism that have emerged at Angkor, as well as why the difficulties brought by rising tourism have been inadequately addressed.

Given recent developments in Cambodia, it contends that Angkor's prominent role within the country's post-conflict cultural and tourist sectors deserves closer, more critical scrutiny.

Figure 2 : Satellite view of Angkor

Figure 3: Map of World Heritage Site of Angkor

Figure 4: Visitor traffic at Angkor Wat

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Figure 5: Tourism infrastructure within the Heritage site of Angkor

Along with Cambodians, numerous tourists visiting Cambodia from different parts of the world have increasingly added to the tourist count which may be projected to be more than a third of a million now (Fig. 4). Due to the overcrowding at Angkor, both visitors and the general public have been subjected to limitations. Access to the most important items of heritage significance has been restricted (Miura, 2006). Figure 5 represents the infrastructure inside Angkor Wat which needs to be strengthened to support the visitor traffic. Angkor has grown in popularity as a destination for various festivities such as the annual Khmer New Year celebrations, social functions, weddings (Fig. 6) and so on. The visits to Angkor are generally characterised by an interweaving of leisure, tourism and religion (Winter, 2004).

Figure 6: Wedding celebrations hosted in the premises of Angkor Wat

SWOT Analysis of the World Heritage site of Angkor

We can readily determine the strengths and weaknesses of the research area by analysing the SWOT matrix. This will assist us in developing effective plans and policies to maximise the strengths while minimising the limitations. The last two parts of the matrix depict the expanding opportunities and potential dangers that stand in the way of long-term growth. We must take steps to turn possibilities into regional strengths and to limit any dangers that may obstruct our progress. Thus, a number of challenges lie in the path of cultural tourism in Angkor. It requires more meticulous vigilance for the sustainability of the sites. The increasing tourism activities, social and cultural events within the heritage site leads to the disturbance of heritage values, cultural & natural environments of the site.

Conclusion

Cultural tourism indeed is a boon for the economic development of a region. To reap the actual benefits of this, proper measures and subsequent infrastructural support is required. Growing tourism industry backed by cultural tourism requires a proper framework which has to be prepared considering different aspects. A holistic approach is needed for the sustainability of the archaeological sites & heritages which will not only consider the structural preservation and conservation but also consider effective strategic planning for providing a sustainable framework for the economy, society, culture & natural environment of that region as well as the neighbouring regions. Thus, the vital question at this juncture remains –Is Cultural Tourism a boon or a threat particularly in case of Angkor? As a matter

of fact, tourism has the potential to be a tremendously positive force, yet there are basic conflicts at its core. Tourism, in the case of Angkor, both simplifies and erases its host environment while reinvigorating and re-creating it. In order to address the difficulties that global tourism poses to places like Angkor Wat, it is important to have the theoretical ability to examine these inconsistencies and formulate adequate strategies.

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